

Data Management Plan – Final

Deliverable D7.3

Grant Agreement n°. 101084234

**Funded by
the European Union**

VERSION HISTORY

Ver.	Date	Comments/Changes	Author/Reviewer
0.1	08/12/2025	Content Review	Maura Farrell
0.2	17/12/2025	Content review	Silvia Sivini, Annie Roos, Helene Ahl, Victor Martinez, Gerdy Verschuure-Stuip, Anastasia Oprea, Willem Korthals Altes, Tuomas Kuhmonen
0.3	19/12/2025	Final review	Coordinator

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Project Acronym	FLIARA
Project Title	FLIARA: Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas
Type of action	HORIZON-RIA
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2022-COMMUNITIES-01-01
Project Start Date	01/01/2023
Project Duration	36 months
Work Package	WP7 Project Management
Deliverable	Data Management Plan- Final
Due Date	31/12/2025
Submission Date	22/12/2025
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Deliverable Responsible	University of Galway
Version	Final
Status	Data Management Plan – Final
Author(s)	Louise Weir, Maura Farrell, Aisling Murtagh University of Galway
Reviewer(s)	Helene Ahl, Annie Roos, Gerdy Verschuure-Stuip, Silvia Sivini, Victor Martinez, Anne Kinsella

¹ PU= Public, SEN= Sensitive.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Table of Contents	2
List of Tables	3
List of Figures	3
Acronyms & Abbreviations	4
1 Introduction.....	5
1.1 Project abstract	5
1.2 Purpose of the Document.....	6
2 Data Summary.....	6
2.1 Data Summary per Work Package	8
3 Fair Data.....	31
3.1 Making Data Findable, Including the Provision of Metadata.....	31
3.2 Making Data Accessible	32
3.3 Making Data Interoperable	34
3.4 Increase Data Reuse.....	35
4 Other Research Elements.....	36
4.1 Other Research Outputs.....	36
4.2 Allocation of Resources.....	37
4.3 Data Security.....	37
4.3.1 Online and networking spaces.....	38
4.4 Ethics	39
4.5 Other.....	42
5 Conclusion.....	42

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Work Package 1 Data Summary	8
Table 2: Work Package 2 Data Summary	11
Table 3: Work Package 3 Data Summary	17
Table 4: Work Package 4 Data Summary	20
Table 5: Work Package 5 Data Summary	23
Table 6: Work Package 6 Data Summary	27
Table 7: Work Package 7 Data Summary	29
Table 8 Peer Reviewed Journal Articles.....	34
Table 9 Data Access at Institution level	38

LIST OF FIGURES

No table of figures entries found.

FLIARA greatly referenced previous DMP by the RURALIZATION Horizon 2020 project.

ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

CoP	Community of Practice
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
WP	Work Package
Project partners	
Galway	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY
TU Delft	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT
TEAGASC	TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY
UNICAL	UNIVERSITA DELLA CALABRIA
LWL	LONGFORD WOMEN S LINK CLG
UTU	TURUN YLIOPISTO
UL	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI
CE	CONSULTA EUROPA PROJECTS AND INNOVATION SL
HNEE	HOCHSCHULE FUR NACHHALTIGE ENTWICKLUNG EBERSWALDE
ELARD	ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE LEADER POURLE DEVELOPPEMENT RURAL
UOULU	OULUN YLIOPISTO
ECOLISE	RESEAU EUROPEEN POUR DES INITIATIVES COMMUNAUTAIRES SUR LES CHANGEMENTS CLIMATIQUES ET LE DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE
MENDELU	MENDELOVA UNIVERZITA V BRNE
LNU	LINNEUNIVERSITETET
HLK	HOGSKOLAN FOR LARANDE OCH KOMMUNIKATION I JONKOPING - HLK SCHOOL OF EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION

1 INTRODUCTION

Horizon Europe is the European Union's research and innovation framework program for the period of 2021-2027, which aims to support research and innovation activities across various scientific disciplines. Data Management Plans, the less known hero of research projects, have a central role in upholding the highest standards and integrity throughout the research lifecycle and ultimately in enabling research projects to achieve their project objectives.

1.1 PROJECT ABSTRACT

Key contemporary trends, such as climate change, gender inequalities and the COVID-19 pandemic, bring new challenges to European rural areas. Change also brings opportunities to foster more resilient, inclusive and sustainable rural regions, such as those created by the digital and ecological transitions. However, there is a need for all individuals and communities to participate in rural innovation. Traditionally, however, rural women's employment opportunities and contribution to innovation has been overshadowed, and often suppressed, by for example a patriarchal ethos. The FLIARA (Female-led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas) project aims to create a European-wide ecosystem, which supports women-led innovative practices in farming and rural areas. This includes different types of rural women, inclusive of age, class, culture, race, and ethnicity who are leading or attempting to engage in rural and farming innovations. The core objective of FLIARA is to ensure that women are embedded in, and supported by, a more effective innovation ecosystem which: spotlights their achievements; provides them with a source of inspiration and knowledge; networks them with key actors engaged in innovation; heightens their visibility within national and international institutional decision-making contexts; increases capacity and improves skills to empower them to continue leading or start leading innovative practices in farming and rural areas. It will create a Community of Practice supporting innovative ecosystems and smart solutions endorsing and encouraging future female innovations and entrepreneurship, until such practice becomes more the norm than the exception. The project will increase understanding of the needs and challenges facing women leading innovative environmental and rural development practices in EU farming and rural areas. In doing this, the project will heighten visibility and awareness of current female-led innovations, and their centrality and importance to achieving EU environmental and inclusion policies.

As a Research Innovation and Action project engaging with stakeholders, gathering, processing and sharing data is the cornerstone of the project. An inclusive, clear and strategic Data Management Plan is the key ingredient to this process and underpins the success of the project.

1.2 PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

This Final Data Management Plan (DMP) builds on D7.1 and D7.2 and provides a consolidated review of how research data generated throughout the Horizon Europe project FLIARA has been collected, documented, processed, stored, shared, and preserved in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and Horizon Europe Open Science requirements. The management of the data produced during the project ensures open access, as stipulated in Article 29.3 of the Grant Agreement, taking also in consideration the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” principle.

During the project, data management practices ensured that all partners adhered to consistent procedures for quality assurance, secure storage, version control, and controlled access. Where possible, datasets have been deposited in trusted open repositories with persistent identifiers, ensuring long-term discoverability and accessibility. Where restrictions apply due to confidentiality, privacy, intellectual property, access conditions are transparently outlined. The project followed community-endorsed metadata standards and open formats to maximise interoperability and reusability. Clear licensing frameworks (e.g., Creative Commons) have been applied to guarantee that data reuse is legally and practically feasible. Data protection was maintained through GDPR-compliant handling of personal data, secure environments for sensitive information, and appropriate anonymisation or pseudonymisation techniques. This document reflects the project’s completed lifecycle, summarising the datasets produced, ethical considerations, and long-term maintenance strategy.

2 DATA SUMMARY

Research data is diverse in format and can be collected using a wide variety of methodologies. In general, it can be described as information generated, collected or observed during a research project. It is evidence used to support research conclusions and will go on to form part of the scholarly record.

Survey and interview text data of a qualitative nature were the dominant data type collected by FLIARA. Survey data was collected as part of WP2 and case studies in WP3 generated text data based on 200 in-depth interviews. A number of focus groups and workshops (WP2, WP4, and WP5) also generated text data in the form of transcripts and/or written notes. This text data took the form of interview transcripts and/or written notes. Recordings of interviews or workshops were stored as .MP3 files, for example. This data had the potential to contain personal data, therefore accessibility was managed in accordance with this fact and in line with the informed consent given by participants. Pictures of female innovators or their innovation formed part of Fact Sheets and Practice Abstracts for WP3 and WP7. Video and audio data (10 podcasts and 10 video blogs) were generated as part of WP4 and WP6 and are accessible through the project website and social media platforms (see D6.3 and D6.5 for more details). Data from public

databases (e.g. Eurostat) and existing publications (e.g. peer reviewed academic papers, policy documents, reports) was used throughout the project as relevant (e.g. concept, literature and policy reviews in WP1, desk-based reviews for case studies in WP3) in accordance with the intellectual property rights governing this data and referenced in reports following a standard referencing method. Tables 1-7 outline the data types, purpose, and format involved in each work package. Where Deliverables have been approved, the link to the repository has been inserted to the table.

Table Key: Text in Yellow box is new data that will be generated by the FLIARA Project.

2.1 DATA SUMMARY PER WORK PACKAGE

Work Package 1 provided the foundation and knowledge base for FLIARA. Each of its four tasks (T1.1 a conceptual framework, T1.2 review of existing knowledge, T1.3 case study assessment and selection framework and T1.4 Assessment of policy and legal frameworks to support policy benchmarking) fed into all other work packages. Data type, purpose and format for WP1 is recorded in Table 1.

Table 1: Work Package 1 Data Summary

WORK PACKAGE 1						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
1.1	Secondary data	Construct conceptual framework for the FLIARA project. Glossary of terms and definitions.	TXT; PDF; DOC	15MB	Open access	Published as a Deliverable (D1.1) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045102 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/18991
1.2	Secondary data	Review of existing knowledge on women-led innovation in farming and rural areas, including appendix on previous European projects	TXT; PDF; DOC	15MB	Open access	Published as a Deliverable (D1.2) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045138 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/18992

WORK PACKAGE 1						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
1.3	Secondary data	Initial guidelines for case study assessment and selection	TXT; PDF; DOC	9 MB	Open access	Published as a Deliverable (D1.4) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045179 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/18994
1.4	Secondary data	Assessment of rural and farming policy and legal frameworks in relation to women-led innovation	TXT; PDF; DOC	10 MB	Open access	Published as a Deliverable (D1.3) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045163 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/18993

WORK PACKAGE 1						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
1.4	Secondary data	Initial Guidelines for policy benchmarking	TXT; PDF; DOC	6 MB	Open access	Published as a Deliverable (D1.5) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045204 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/18995

*CORDIS: European Commission's primary public repository for information on all EU-funded research projects and their outcomes.

Work Package 2 employed Futures Research, foresight and trend analysis, to envision the role of women in the innovations demanded for sustainable farm and rural futures. It contained three tasks which were all linked together both process-wise and content-wise and it took place across nine European regional contexts (located in Germany, Ireland and The Netherlands (Atlantic); Czech Republic and Slovenia (Central/Eastern); Finland and Sweden (Nordic/Baltic) as well as Italy and Spain (Mediterranean). Research guidelines and data management for all three tasks were produced in M02 and are contained in D2.1 Research Guidelines for Foresight and Trend Analysis. The activities of WP2 included acquisition and analysis of three main types of data: workshop data, interview data and survey data. Table 2 outlines the data summary for WP2.

Table 2: Work Package 2 Data Summary

WORK PACKAGE 2						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
2.1	New data: workshop and interview data	Identify sustainability innovations for 9 regions	MP3; WAV; DOC.	90 visions	This is available to researchers on the project. This data will not be shared for reuse as it may contain personal data	

WORK PACKAGE 2						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
2.1	Processed Workshop and interview data	Identify sustainability innovations for 9 regions	Excel file	90 visions	Open access	Published as annexes of the report (D2.2) on the FLIARA website and also available CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045244 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/18997
2.1	Secondary data	Research Guidelines for Foresight and Trend Analysis	TXT; PDF; DOC	15MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable in the form of a report (D2.1) on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045235 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/18996

WORK PACKAGE 2						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
2.1	Interview, workshop data and secondary data	Report detailing visions manifesting sustainable farm and rural futures in nine regional contexts	TXT; PDF; DOC	15MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable in the form of a report (D2.2) on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045244 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/18997
2.2	New Data: Workshop and interview data	Identify sustainability innovations for 9 regions	MP3; WAV; DOC;	540-720 innovations	This is only available to researchers on the research group that carried out the interviews. This data will not be shared for reuse as it may contain personal data.	

WORK PACKAGE 2						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
2.2	Processed Workshop and interview data	Identify sustainability innovations for 9 regions	Excel file	540-720 innovations	Open	Published as annex (D2.3) of the report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045277 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/19000
2.2	Workshop, interview data and secondary data	Report detailing sustainability innovations needed to realise the visions in each context	TXT; PDF; DOC	3-15 MB	Open	Published as Deliverable in the form of a report (D2.3) on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045277 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/19000

WORK PACKAGE 2						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
2.3	New Data: Workshop and interview data	Assess the potential for women's contribution to sustainability innovations	TXT; WAV; DOC;	60-80 assessments	This is only available to researchers on the research group that carried out the workshops. This data will not be shared for reuse as it may contain personal data.	
2.3	Workshop and interview data	Assess the potential for women's contribution to sustainability innovations	TXT; PDF; DOC	60-80 assessments	Open	Published as annexes of the report (D2.4) on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045295 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/19001

WORK PACKAGE 2						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
2.3	Evidence from T2.1, T2.2, T2.3 and secondary data	To report the specification of women's contribution to the sustainability innovations in each context.	TXT; PDF; DOC	3-15 MB	Open	Published as Deliverable in the form of a report (D2.4) on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045295 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/19001

The aim of Work Package 3 was to deepen understanding of the pathways to success and the challenges facing women-led sustainability innovation in farming and rural areas. It directly engaged with 200 female innovators and entrepreneurs through coordinating 20 case studies, 10 via women-led innovations in farming and 10 via rural areas. Research Guidelines to lead this investigation was produced in M12, D 3.1 Research Guidelines and Thematic Selection. Using a case study approach data collection was qualitative and involved the use of a semi-structured interview guide. With the consent of the respondent, recording of data was via note taking and/or audio and/or video recording. During field activities, it was recommended that pertinent grey literature (such as newsletters, bulletins, fact sheets, reports, project publications, newspaper/magazine articles) related to the specific project/practice should be collected. A key output of WP3 was the production of 200 fact sheets showcasing the innovations of the interviewees. For this purpose, with the explicit consent of the interviewee, at least one photograph of the location/initiative or of the woman was retrieved. Table 3 outlines the data summary for WP3.

Table 3: Work Package 3 Data Summary

WORK PACKAGE 3						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
3.1	Original created text- Guidelines	Research guidelines and thematic selection	TXT; PDF; DOC	8 MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable (D3.1) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045325 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/19005

WORK PACKAGE 3						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
3.1	Secondary data involving a scoping review of female-led innovation providing an inventory of innovations to support case study selection	Inventory of female-led innovations	TXT; PDF; DOC	10 MB	Only the sensitised data for project reports (where all anonymity was applied) is Open. All data with potential sensitivity is retained in secure partner files.	Once synthesised, relevant material was published as a Deliverable (D3.2) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045348 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/19006
3.2	New Data: Interviews	Gather new data to identify barriers and opportunities; drivers and enablers	MP3; MP4, .jpg, .pdf, .doc	40MB 200 interviews	This is only available to researchers in the research group that carried out the interviews. This data will not be shared for reuse as it may contain personal data	

WORK PACKAGE 3						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
3.3	Assessment of Case Study material	Lessons learned on women led innovations in agriculture and rural areas Fact sheets on female innovations	TXT; PDF; DOC; .jpg	200 fact sheets 80 MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable D3.3 on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045390 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/19007
3.4	Knowledge from Task 3.3	Comparative analysis report reflecting insights by macro-region and the European level	TXT; PDF; DOC	9 MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable (D3.4) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository
3.4	Knowledge from T3.2 and T3.3	Create 10 Practice abstracts based on the outcomes of the 20 case studies (T3.3) and the comparative analysis of case studies (T3.4).	TXT; PDF; DOC	3 MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable (D3.5) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website (https://fliara.eu/practice-abstracts/) and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository. Once approved they will be published on the EIP-Agri platform and in the Farm Book platform.

Work Package 4 was responsible for establishing the FLIARA Community of Practice Network which provides an interchange platform for multi-actor exchanges where the 20 FLIARA women Ambassadors are centre stage. It was also integral to the development of the FLIARA toolkit. A Strategic Action Plan was developed in M16 (D4.1 Strategic Action Plan) which provided a detailed plan, including for data management and ethics, for delivering the four Community of Practice Networking events. This WP involved interaction with key stakeholders and involved focus groups and workshops through online and in-person events. Participation in all activities was governed through the consent procedure set out in D8.1 and D4.1, which facilitated the recording of data for research purposes. Data collection during these events was through note taking, audio and/or video with findings feeding into WP4 and WP5 Deliverables. Task 4.4 aimed to leverage partner experience and evidence from WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP6 to create the FLIARA Toolkit. The Toolkit is hosted on the FLIARA Website and features various training and knowledge tools, including Innovation Fact Sheets, Podcasts, Video Blogs, and a Gender-Specific Guide to Innovation. Table 4 details all data summary for WP4.

Table 4: Work Package 4 Data Summary

WORK PACKAGE 4						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
4.1	Secondary data	Strategic Action Plan for delivering the four Community of Practice Networking events	TXT; PDF; DOC; .jpg	3 MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable (D4.1) in the form of a report CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045414 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/19008

WORK PACKAGE 4						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
4.2	Community of practice	Networking event to share knowledge	MP3; DOC; MP4; .Jpg; YouTube Server (.FLV)	40GB	This is available to researchers on the project. This data will not be shared for reuse as it may contain personal data	
4.2	Community of Practice Workshops	Collection of knowledge from the outcomes of the Four Community of Practice Networking events	TXT; PDF; DOC; .Jpg	8 MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable (D4.2) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository
4.3	Focus groups and workshops	Gather new data to assess findings and garner feedback	DOC; TXT;.Jpg	9 MB	This is available to researchers on the project. This data will not be shared for reuse as it may contain personal data	

WORK PACKAGE 4						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
4.3	Focus groups and workshops	Policy Design and Benchmarking	TXT; PDF; DOC; Jpg	8 MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable (D4.3) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository
4.4	Evidence from WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6	FLIARA Toolkit. Fact Sheets, Podcasts, Video Blogs and a Gender Specific Guide to Innovation	Multiple-DOC; MP3; MP4; WAV; PDF; .Jpg; YouTube Server (.FLV)	15MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable (D4.4) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository
4.5	Evidence from WP 1, 2, 3, 4	Gender specific Guide to Female Led Innovation in Farming and Rural areas drawing together good practice and key lessons learned relating to drivers, obstacles, enablers and pathways for female-led rural innovation	PDF	19 MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable (D4.5) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository

The main objective of Work Package 5 is to design more effective policy and governance frameworks, as well as knowledge and innovation systems, using insights from the project to enhance women-led innovation in farming and rural areas. In addition to leveraging results from WP1-WP5, this WP will also use secondary data sources and data collected through focus groups and workshops (T5.2, T5.3) to inform its outputs. This WP commenced in M18 and concludes in M36. Table 5 outlines the data summary for WP5.

Table 5: Work Package 5 Data Summary

WORK PACKAGE 5						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
5.1/5.2	Evidence from WP 1, 2, 3, 4	Policy Booklet and Policy Brief	TXT; PDF; DOC	22 MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable (D5.1), in the form of a Policy Booklet on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository

WORK PACKAGE 5						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
5.1	Evidence from WP 1, 3, 4	Inform Gender Bench Marking.	TXT; PDF; DOC	7 MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable (D5.3), in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository
5.3	New Data: Focus groups	To discuss findings and garner feedback	PDF; DOC	5 MB	Open. All data is included in the Annexes of D5.2.	Published in the Annexes of Deliverable D5.2, in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository.

WORK PACKAGE 5						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
5.3	Processed focus group transcripts and material from within the project	To outline the process and outcomes of participatory scenario development and testing, and include the finalised scenario text	TXT; PDF; DOC	7 MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable (D5.2), in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository
5.4	New data: Policy Practice Workshop	To discuss findings and garner feedback	DOC; Jpeg	30MB	This is available to researchers on the project that carried out the work. The data is made anonymous during the process of summarising and only general lines of discussions are published. This data will not be shared for reuse as it may contain personal data.	

WORK PACKAGE 5						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
5.4	Processed policy workshop transcripts and material from within the project	Report on policy workshop with policy makers at EU and other governance levels.	TXT; PDF; DOC	30 MB	Only processed data that forms part of published material will be open	Published as a Deliverable (D5.4), in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository

Work Package 6 is responsible for communication, dissemination and exploitation activities for FLIARA. WP6 activities are core to the success of FLIARA and run for the lifetime of the project. Through strategic and innovative approaches WP6 synthesises and ensures that outputs from FLIARA reaches its target audiences. Deliverables, D6.1, D6.2, D6.3, D6.4 and D6.5 hold detailed guidelines in relation to the use, dissemination and exploitation of FLIARA results and outputs. Table 6 outlines the data summary for WP6.

Table 6: Work Package 6 Data Summary

WORK PACKAGE 6						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
6.1	Secondary Data	To guide activities for WP6	TXT; PDF; DOC	15MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable (D6.1) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045427 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/19009
6.1	Evidence from D6.1	To guide activities for WP6	TXT; PDF; DOC	5MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable (D6.2) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045443 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/19010

WORK PACKAGE 6						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
6.1	Evidence from D6.1, D6.2	To guide activities for WP6	TXT; PDF; DOC	15MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable (D6.3) in the form of a report on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository
6.1	Project content	Develop a Project website	HTML	5MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable (D6.4). Available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045470 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/19012
6.4	Female Innovators	10 podcasts	MP3; MP4; WAV	5 GB	Open	On FLIARA website and social media
6.4	Female Innovators	10 video Blogs (interviews)	MP3; MP4; YouTube Server FLV	5 GB	Open	On FLIARA website and social media

Work Package 7 worked to ensure an effective management of the project through close collaboration and collegiality with all partners. Data sources for use during WP7 is garnered from other WP's and secondary data sources. Table 7 outlines the data summary for WP7.

Table 7: Work Package 7 Data Summary

WORK PACKAGE 7						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
7.1	From the project and secondary sources	Data Management Plan V1	TXT; PDF; DOC	7 MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable, D7.1 on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045488 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/19013
7.3	From D7.1 and material from the Project	Data Management Plan V2	TXT; PDF; DOC	7 MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable, D7.2 on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository https://zenodo.org/records/14045502 https://hdl.handle.net/10379/19014

WORK PACKAGE 7						
Task	Type of data	Purpose of data	Format of data	Expected size of data	Accessibility of data	Availability of data
7.3	From D7.1. D7.2 and material from the Project	Data Management Plan Final	TXT; PDF; DOC	7 MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable, D7.3 on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository
7.1	Evidence from knowledge across the other WPs	4 Practice Abstracts were required in the Grant Agreement. 15 were produced.	TXT; PDF; DOC	9 MB	Open	Published as a Deliverable, (D7.4) on the FLIARA website and also available on CORDIS*, Zenodo, University of Galway Research Repository. Once approved they will be published on the EIP-Agri platform and in the Farm Book platform.
7.5	Research ethics approval and monitoring	Ethics Approval	TXT; PDF; DOC	9 MB	Sensitive	Sensitive Data D8.1 H - POPD - Requirement No. 1. Sets out the 'ethics requirements' that the project must comply with.

The data generated from the whole project is securely stored in the partner organisations own trusted data repositories (password protected and encrypted) by the partner responsible for collecting the data. However, where facilities were not available in partner organisations, partners cooperated in their regional groupings to ensure these requirements were met. All publications (e.g. deliverables, peer-reviewed papers) emerging from FLIARA will be open access. The Co-Ordinator has and will oversee this process.

3 FAIR DATA

FAIR stands for findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. These principles are intended as guidelines for best practice in the management and stewardship of research data with a focus on facilitating sharing and reuse of valuable research outputs.

3.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING THE PROVISION OF METADATA

Data discovery, re-use and reproducibility is dependent on high quality documentation and metadata. Collecting supporting documentation or metadata during active research is what allows FAIRification and data sharing further down the line. Research outputs from FLIARA adhere to the FAIR principles through the following process.

Data from workshops, interviews and focus groups have been recorded (video e.g. MP3, .wav), and transcribed (text e.g. Word) and analysed using software such as SPSS, Excel and or NVIVO. This data has been and will only be shared within the research team that undertook the data collection and available to auditors for verification. However, a metadata record, where relevant, for the data will be published in the Zenodo repository, making it discoverable in a searchable resource online. Though the data is not available publicly this will enable others to discover and learn about the dataset. Zenodo assigns a persistent identifier (DOI) to the dataset. The dataset record in Zenodo includes the following metadata where applicable:

- Author/Principal Investigator/Data Creator
- Publication date/Release Date
- Title of Data Source
- Version/Edition Number
- Format of the Data
- Publisher, Resource type
- Persistent Identifier e.g. DOI
- Publication Place

Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE programme and operated by CERN, allowing paper, reports research software, etc. to be deposited for public access.

All of the aforementioned new data (including transcripts of interviews, which will not be provided openly) will be retained for at least seven years (4 years post Project as defined in the Joint Controller Agreement) on the servers of the project partner responsible for gathering this new data (this data is often in the local language of that partner; and it is better not to transfer unnecessary personal data between partners) for the purposes of validation. Each partner will ensure that there will be people curating the new data during this period. The servers for storing all new data has the necessary security mechanisms, such as password protections, restricted access only to the project partner.

Datasets, where relevant, are accompanied by rich metadata (adhering to Dublin Core) to ensure they are findable. In addition, to further aid their discoverability, keywords describing the datasets have been and will be added. Every dataset has been and will be also assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), to make them citable and persistently available. In addition, FLIARA will adhere to the Data Documentation Initiative standard for disciplinary-specific, rich description of all the data files created when applicable.

All data files employed a specified naming convention. The specific details have been outlined in the FLIARA Project Management Handbook. The following elements were used in the file name:

- Date: YYYYMMDD
- Descriptive file name
- Initials of the person who last modified the file

Data, which can be made openly accessible, will be submitted to a relevant repository within 6 months after the approval of the deliverable they have contributed to.

3.2 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

FLIARA data was deposited in compliance with HE rules on open access, in a number of repositories, and under open licenses. FLIARA systematically adhered to the Open Science practices and principles set out in Article 17 of the HORIZON Europe Model Grant Agreement (MGA) and its Annex 5, throughout the entirety of the project, from inception to completion. It contributed to this by sharing anonymised scientific data and knowledge arising from the project with all relevant knowledge actors, in a transparent and non-discriminatory manner. This was made as open as possible and activated as early as possible throughout the research process.

Access to new data (including transcripts of interviews) for the validation of the results will be possible under strict access conditions. The responsible project partners will ensure access upon request is solely for this purpose and in line with data management and ethic requirements.

It was established at the outset that FLIARA data, which can be made openly accessible, would be submitted to a repository within 6 months after the approval of the deliverable

they have contributed to and will be deposited in compliance with HE rules on open access, in a trusted repository and under open licenses e.g. Creative Commons licence 'CC-BY'. All approved FLIARA deliverables and project outputs have been made openly available through multiple repositories, including CORDIS, Zenodo, EIP Agri, EU FarmBook and the University of Galway Research Repository (formerly known as ARAN). Please see D6.3 for more specific details for dissemination and exploitation. Links to these platforms per each Deliverable are in Tables 1-7 above.

FLIARA, through the work of Consulta Europa, established a FLIARA Zenodo Community within Zenodo. This not only holds the FLIARA open access material but also encourages other researchers with similar themed materials to publish within this community. This has served to build a community of researchers and raise the profile of Women-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas.

Furthermore, the project, through its Grant Agreement, also committed to engaging in the publication of materials to maximise the reach and impact of the project. The Grant Agreement notes the production of 3 FLIARA annual newsletters, 3 scientific publications and 15 non-scientific publications, alongside 20 press releases (please see D6.3 for more specific details). Thus far, the project has exceeded its commitments and in relation to peer reviewed article publications it has produced 4 peer reviewed articles with others under construction. Of specific relevance is the submission of these 4 articles to open access journals (Table 8). The University of Galway have also signed a contract with Edward Elgar Publishing to publish a book, with open access, from the project titled "Policy Infrastructures for Female-Led Rural Innovation". Coordinated by the University of Galway and featuring chapters from consortium partners (LWL, Teagasc, TU Delft, HNEE, UL, UTU, MENDELU, UNICAL, OULU, ECOLISE, ELARD, LNU, HLK, and CE), this book is due for publication in 2026.

Publication/Journal	Title	Date Published	Link
European Countryside (Sciendo)	Empowering Women-Led Innovations: Key Players In Realising The Long-Term Vision For Rural Areas	Dec 22, 2024	https://sciendo.com/article/10.2478/euco-2024-0029
Dela (University of Ljubljana)	PROJEKT FLIARA: TRAJNOSTNI RAZVOJ PODEŽELJA, NOVI PRISTOPI, VLOGA IN MOČ ŽENSK <i>(FLIARA Project: Sustainable Rural Development, New Approaches, Role and Empowerment of Women)</i>	Dec 30, 2024	https://journals.uni-lj.si/Dela/issue/view/1444/1130

<p>European Public Mosaic (EPuM)</p>	<p>Breaking barriers: how women are transforming agriculture and rural innovation</p>	<p>May 21, 2025</p>	<p>https://www.gencat.cat/eapc/epum/N26/index.html#page=107</p>
<p>Rural and Regional Development</p>	<p>Gendered Mismatches in the Business Support System in Rural Sweden</p>	<p>Oct 28, 2025</p>	<p>https://www.sciepublis.com/article/pii/752</p>

Table 8 Peer Reviewed Journal Articles

All partners aiming to publish in any peer reviewed publications with data emerging from FLIARA post Project end date, are committed to acknowledgement to the Funder of the research and ensuring open access through a trusted repository, whether the publication is free of charge or not and with content licensed for re-use. Selecting the right data repository ensures the long-term preservation and availability of research data/outputs. This allows the project to leverage the infrastructure of the repository to FAIRify the data.

The availability of project outputs as Open Access through such collaborative, dissemination platforms further improve the accessibility to, and the reusability of, research outputs from this project. It also ensures greater citation counts for academic publications and reports in the long term.

3.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

FLIARA utilised open and standardised file formats, standards (e.g. Data Documentation Initiative) and controlled vocabularies to maximise interoperability where applicable.

3.4 INCREASE DATA REUSE

An important strategy for demonstrating research transparency is to create comprehensive documentation that captures important details of the research process so that others are able to follow it to reproduce published research results.

Data consists of generally accepted formats. Most of the data for FLIARA was qualitative and was analysed using SPSS, Excel or NVIVO program. The data formats for SPSS-data are sav-format and for video and audio recordings .mp4 and .mp3 format. Transcripts and content coding was in .docx format. Where generated, quantitative data was processed and analysed by using SPSS and excel statistical programs. All other materials, such as questionnaires were saved as, for example, .pdf-files, DOC, TXT. Used software and formats were based on open standards to enable data reuse, interoperability and sharing.

README.txt files were used to store structural (naming conventions and purpose of folders and files) and administrative (e.g., when the files and folders were created, file types and other technical information, and who can access it) metadata. The datasets that are included in a repository, are licensed under a CC-BY licence, which requires attribution/credit for the original creation, while at the same time ensuring broadest possible re-use. Datasets, which can be made openly accessible, will be made publicly available within 6 months of European Commission's approval of the deliverable that is based on the dataset, allowing the necessary time to publish.

Zenodo (where the datasets were deposited) ensures data quality and curation (manual curation at the time of deposition, and automated curation and checks for data integrity after the deposit). Metadata was provided where relevant. Material submitted to Zenodo will be held in line with their retention period, which currently relates to the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

The reusability and usefulness of outputs is important to consider in the context of dissemination, impact and legacy. FLIARA has identified a number of specific target groups, namely, scientific, industry, policy makers and citizens. Therefore, outputs will not only be in accessible language but each of these target groups will be able to find relevant material in the outputs and use them as resources within their own field of expertise (please see D6.3, D6.5 and D4.5 for more specific details in relation to dissemination, exploitation and the FLIARA toolkit). Additionally, outputs contain clear citations and references so that information can be reused for comparative purposes.

4 OTHER RESEARCH ELEMENTS

The FAIR principles require a DMP to consider all aspects of data management during and after the life of the project. Reusability and exploitation of results are central tenets of Horizon Europe projects.

4.1 OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

A fundamental purpose of the FLIARA project was the creation of a freely available and easily accessible resources on the project's website aimed at stimulation and assisting women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas. As per Tables 1-7 above, FLIARA produced outputs outside of Data files, for example, Video and audio data (10 podcasts and 10 video blogs) have been generated as part of WP4 and WP6 (Please see D6.3 and D6.5 for more details). These have been published on the FLIARA website, fliara.eu, and on the FLIARA social media platforms. Policies and regulations safeguarding the use of this content is via consent forms which have been approved through institutions ethical approval (outlined in D8.1) and further regulations for use on the channels of communication and dissemination are documented in Deliverables D6.3 and D6.4. For example, the FLIARA website has already installed an SSL certificate. An SSL certificate provides a secure, encrypted connection between the website and its users, protecting against potential interception or tampering with sensitive data. By incorporating this certificate, users can trust that their data is being transmitted securely when they interact with the website. The website has also been designed with users' privacy in mind. It already includes a privacy policy, which outlines the type of personal information that may be collected, how it is used, and how users can exercise their rights in relation to their data by accessing to <https://fliara.eu/privacy-policy/>. FLIARA's website is also compliant with the GDPR. To help users manage their cookie preferences, the website includes a plugin for cookies management. In addition to this FLIARA adhered to ownership, access rights and IPR protection principles defined in the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA), following Horizon Europe principles. The Consortium Agreement (CA) sets out the rules for the use of foreground/ background knowledge and the rules for handling sensitive and confidential information. D6.3 details the process of protecting IPR through its IPR Strategy and checklist by assessing results, including their exploitation potential in the project's exploitation plan (D6.3).

D6.3 details the process that was undertaken to establish the most suitable Creative Commons licence. The standard licensing decision for all core project outputs (including reports, publications, and data) was set as CC BY 4.0 (Attribution), as confirmed under D6.1. This permissive license promotes maximum sharing and reuse, even for commercial purposes, provided proper attribution is given. The use of a CC BY-SA 4.0 (Attribution-ShareAlike) licence was also considered for methodological tools where the consortium wanted to ensure that any future derivative works remain equally open. All finalised licensing decisions were clearly documented via templates and communicated to all partners (D6.3).

Regarding post-project sustainability of end user materials produced by the project, there will also be no IPR barriers to continued use of this content at the end of this project. CE guarantees the technical hosting and maintenance of the website and toolkit for a minimum of two years post-project (until 31 December 2027). This commitment, alongside the open-access licensing (CC-BY) of all final deliverables, material on open repositories, guarantees that FLIARA's complete body of work remains a permanent, citable, and easily exploitable resource for all future users.

4.2 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

The costs of archiving the data will be borne by the project partner responsible for keeping the data. The costs of data management are part of the project costs of the Horizon Europe project and data management is part of the regular management structure of the project and commitments made under the Joint Controller Agreement.

4.3 DATA SECURITY

University of Galway (as the Coordinator) is primarily responsible for the managing of project documents. FLIARA consortium used MS Teams as a collaborative and storage space. It provided robust managed storage with automatic backup services. It is only accessible via login, hence access and editing rights can be managed thus providing data security. File and folder naming conventions were established and maintained.

Documentation relating to the FLIARA project will be securely stored on the Sharepoint server for up to 4 years after the completion of the project. It enforces team-wide and organisation-wide two-factor authentication, single sign-on through Active Directory, and encryption of data in transit and at rest. Files are stored in SharePoint and are backed by SharePoint encryption. It follows the same guidance and principles as the Microsoft Trust Centre. For more information <https://www.microsoft.com/en-ie/trust-center?rtc=1>.

Data gathered during the project is also securely stored in the partner organisations own trusted data repositories (password protected and encrypted) by the partner responsible for collecting the data (as approved by partners ethical agreements D8.1). Research organisations, working with the research data, in the project had facilities to comply with requirements to storage, back-up procedures and access to research data. However, where facilities were not available in partner organisations, partners cooperated in their regional groupings to ensure these requirements were met (as defined in the DoA).

Guidelines for collecting and storing interview data in WP2 and WP3 that was gathered in a local context outlined that interviewers were guided to upload audio files (of interviews) and text files of transcriptions at least once per working day to a secure data server. If in a remote rural context of a specific case study no workable safe connection to the server is available, this upload was permitted to be postponed a few days until such a connection became available.

Only personnel working on the project have access to data files. Responsible for data access at each partner are the following persons:

PARTNER	PERSONNEL
Galway	Maura Farrell
TU Delft	Willem Korthals Altes
TEAGASC	Anne Kinsella
UNICAL	Silvia Sivini
LWL	Tara Farrell
UTU	Tuomas Kuhmonen
UL	Barbara Lampič
CE	Michelle Perello
HNEE	Susanne Von Muenchhausen
ELARD	Marion Eckardt
UOULU	Simo Sarkki
ECOLISE	Eamon O Hara; Anastasia Oprea
MENDELU	Milada Stastna
LNU	Annie Roos
HLK	Helene Ahl

Table 9 Data Access at Institution level

To account for accidental loss of documents all partners engaged with best practice which states that researchers should maintain three copies of their data, two on different media and one off-site. As the Coordinator, University of Galway, had and continues to have the support of the Data Protection Officer at University of Galway to provide additional advice, as needed, on data management during the research project.

4.3.1 ONLINE AND NETWORKING SPACES

The FLIARA project utilises a project website, <https://www.fliara.eu/>, and social media platforms to engage end users for the purposes of knowledge sharing and capacity building. As outlined in D6.4, D6.3, D6.5, D7.1, D7.2 and D8.1, a number of measures were put in place to support this process. The website includes a privacy policy, is compliant with the GDPR and includes a plugin for cookies management. A Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificate has been installed on the website (a more detailed description is contained in D6.4).

An online component of the FLIARA Community of Practice (CoP) was established under WP6. LinkedIn was the chosen platform to serve as a space for knowledge sharing and communication among those with a shared goal to promote and advance women led innovations. D4.1 outlined the professional conduct, privacy setting, confidentiality awareness and reporting protocol in relation to interacting on the LinkedIn Platform. D4.2 details the transition of the LinkedIn space as the project closes in December 2005. Participants have been notified that the official FLIARA Community of Practice LinkedIn Group (current members: 150+) will be kept active by CE as a legacy knowledge-sharing platform for continued dialogue among policymakers, researchers, and practitioners.

4.4 ETHICS

The approach of the FLIARA project to respond to requirements in HE Regulation 2021/695: Eligible actions and ethical principles (Article 18) and Ethics (Article 19), Article 14 and Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement, has been set out in Deliverable, D8.1 – H - POPD - Requirement No. 1. Deliverable 8.1 also contains all documents in relation to partner's individual ethics approval.

As set out in D8.1 the following documents guide the actions of the consortia:

- ALLEA European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity
- Global Code of Conduct for Research in Resource-poor Settings
- The Helsinki Declaration in its latest version (2013);
- The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ECCRI, 2011);
- The EU Charter on Fundamental Rights (CFREU, 2010);
- The UNESCO Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights (2005);
- The European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR, 1950);
- The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR, 1948).

All consortium members received a copy of the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA 2017). All FLIARA researchers adhered to their own institutions' and national ethical guidelines, for example, the Coordinator University of Galway has two ethics committees each responsible for granting approval for research work depending on the nature of the proposed work. Its policies and procedures are available at QA512-Research-Ethics-Committee.pdf

(<https://www.universityofgalway.ie/media/innovation/files/QA512-Research-Ethics-Committee.pdf>) which defines the essential principles of research integrity, responsibility and transparency.

FLIARA researchers were aware that they were accountable towards their employers, funders, as well as, on more ethical grounds, towards society as a whole. They adhered to the principles of sound, transparent and efficient financial management and cooperate with any authorised audits of their research, whether undertaken by their employers/funders or by ethics committees. The consortium adhered to the principles laid down in the Charter of Fundamental Rights and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union that privacy and data protection are fundamental rights which need to be protected at all times. Data will be handled in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation) of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data. The consortium furthermore observed all relevant national legislations for the countries, all belonging to the EU, where data was collected, processed, and stored. The FLIARA project objectives and methodology involved human participants in the research process. Minors under the age of 18 were not involved. Data that could be affected by ethical issues centred in on WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5. The FLIARA objectives and methodology in WP2 involved qualitative (focus groups) and quantitative (surveys) data

gathering techniques. These methods were used to conduct futures research envisioning the role of women in the innovations demanded for sustainable farm and rural futures. This data collection was guided by its own specific research guidelines, Deliverable D2.1. In WP3, qualitative methods took the form of research interviews to understand pathways and challenges facing women-led innovations in farming and rural areas. This research was guided by Deliverable D3.1. In WP4 and WP5 focus groups and workshops were carried out in relation to gender benchmarking, policy discussion and policy scenario development. Engagement in this research involved reflecting and drawing on the participants professional activities (e.g. female innovators, representatives of local organisations, policymakers). Informed consent procedures and participant information sheets ensured that participants were clear about what their involvement entailed. This research element did not result in personal and sensitive data emerging. However, partners were cognisant that there was potential in the data collection process that personal and sensitive data could have still emerged meaning that data must be treated confidentially. Therefore, during the process of data processing, each partner was responsible for anonymising identity as much as possible. If full anonymisation was not possible in the context provided, pseudonymisation was used. All the de-identification conditions and protection mechanism was clarified in the consent form provided to all participants. Participants were asked to sign consent forms in advance of their participation and provided with information related to the nature of the research. Detailed guidelines for data processing, anonymisation, consent forms and participant information sheets is contained in D8.1. The guides produced in D8.1 were followed to produce consent forms and participant information sheets related to activities linked to different work packages (see D2.1, D2.3, D3.1 and D4.1 for activity specific consent forms and participant information sheets). FLIARA upheld its commitment to always be fully transparent with individuals in terms of its use and safeguarding of personal data, including by providing this information in easily accessible, concise, easy to understand and clear language. This commitment and continuity in Data management and ethics across all work packages has been illustrated during the production of one of the final Deliverables, D4.5 Gender Specific Guide to Female-Led Innovation in Farming and Rural Areas.

D4.5 draws on and synthesises results from WP1–WP6, so no new data collection was necessary. All information used had already been gathered with appropriate consent from the FLIARA Innovators earlier in the project. In keeping with FLIARA’s core ethos of placing women at the centre of all activities, the draft Guide was shared with all those mentioned to ensure that the messages presented accurately reflected their intentions. Although this additional step did not result in substantial changes to the Guide, it strongly reaffirmed the value of adhering to ethical and data-management principles. It strengthened the trust between the *researchers* and the *researched* and, at the same time, enhanced the quality of the research, supporting its wider dissemination.

FLIARA adhered to ownership, access rights and IPR protection principles defined in the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA), following Horizon Europe principles. FLIARA researchers adopted safe working practices, in line with national legislation, including taking the necessary precautions for health and safety and for recovery from information technology disasters, e.g. by preparing proper back-up strategies. University of Galway as Coordinator will act as ethical issues ombudsman and was available at all times to discuss any issues which may have arisen.

A key message in D8.1 was the core belief within the Consortium that ethics is not 'red tape' for research but empowers researchers to do the right thing for society and to build trust grounded in core values and fundamental rights such as human dignity, privacy protection and security. To embed this ethos in our practices, a number of measures were put in place.

- A FLIARA Ethics Mentor role was established, the process of this is documented in D8.1. This position was filled by a consortium member that has expert knowledge of ethics. Their role was to support consortium members in complying to commitments and to also build capacity within the Consortium regarding approaches to the incorporation of ethical principles and values through practices and collaboration throughout the life of FLIARA.
- A FLIARA Community of Practice Ethics Guardian role was established, the process of this is documented in D4.1. The FLIARA CoP Ethics Guardian provided support to the 20 women FLIARA Ambassadors for the 18-month period (under the regulation of FLIARA) of the FLIARA CoP. A two-part process was developed to enable the Ethics Guardian to monitor and support the well-being of the Ambassadors. In addition to this, the Ethics CoP Guardian attended each in-person event and was available to Ambassadors for meetings and the contact details of the Ethics Guardian was shared with the Ambassadors to facilitate communication over the 18-month period of the FLIARA CoP.
- An Ambassadors Guide to FLIARA was prepared to provide Ambassadors with an accessible overview of FLIARA. It also contained details regarding the operation of the FLIARA Community of Practice (CoP) and the role and involvement of Ambassadors.
- A detailed monitoring and evaluation procedure was established for Community of Practice events. This involved feedback from all participants of the Community of Practice. Monitoring and evaluation enabled the consortium to gather valuable insights, promote added value, improvement and ensure accountability. In this way it supported evidence-based decision making and enabled adaptation to changing circumstances (see D4.1 and D4.2 for more specific details).

In Reporting Period 2, FLIARA was subject to a formal Ethics Assessment. The report found that the project had exceeded its mandatory obligations resulting in the decision that:

“There is no need for ethics requirements because the consortium shows an excellent ethics awareness and a robust monitoring process extended to all members of the consortium (appointment of an Ethics Mentor, inclusion of a Joint Controller Agreement in the Consortium Agreement, appointment of an Ethics Guardian).. the Deliverables submitted under the guidance of the Ethics Mentor are deemed sufficient and so is the ethical oversight. Therefore, no need to appoint an Ethics Advisor or Ethics Advisory Board”.

4.5 OTHER

A Joint Controller Agreement was required under section 4.4 of the Consortium Agreement. This data sharing agreement was fully executed on the 20/06/2023.

5 CONCLUSION

Data management is not consigned to one partner or one work package, its success lies in its central position of the project and the firm belief of the whole Consortium that project outcomes and outputs are dependent on the approach to and treatment of data during its whole lifecycle. With this perspective as a starting point, FLIARA has been able to deliver on its commitment to produce robust evidence-based research to inform and advance the agenda of women led innovation in agriculture and rural areas.

Embracing the guidelines and regulations surrounding best practice for Data Management now means that the data provided by FLIARA will continue to support the legacy of FLIARA through dissemination and exploitation of data and results; improving access and reuse of research data; and knowledge sharing with citizens, the wider public, interested stakeholders, and the scientific community.

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas

